

Rising Incidence of Candidemia in Neonatal Intensive Care and Sick Newborn Units at a Tertiary Care Hospital

Deepak Kumar¹, Kishore Kumar Sinha²

¹Junior Resident (PG Student), MD (Paediatrics), Department of Paediatrics, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

Received: 09-03-2024 / Revised: 30-03-2024 / Accepted: 12-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Kishore Kumar Sinha

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Candidemia, a serious bloodstream infection caused by *Candida* species, is a growing concern in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) and sick newborn care units (SNCUs) worldwide. Neonates, particularly those with low birth weight and prematurity, are at high risk due to their underdeveloped immune systems and frequent exposure to invasive medical procedures.

Aim: To assess the incidence, risk factors, and outcomes of candidemia in neonates.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted, including 150 neonates. Blood cultures were obtained to identify candidemia, and relevant clinical data were collected. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to identify significant risk factors and outcomes associated with candidemia.

Results: The incidence of candidemia was 14.7%, with *Candida albicans* being the most commonly isolated species (50%). Significant risk factors identified included low birth weight (OR: 4.25, p=0.001), central venous catheter use (OR: 3.76, p=0.002), and broad-spectrum antibiotic use (OR: 2.88, p=0.015). Candidemia was associated with a higher mortality rate (45.5%) and longer hospital stays (mean: 28.5 days) compared to neonates without candidemia.

Conclusion: Candidemia remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality among neonates in intensive care. Low birth weight, central venous catheter use, and broad-spectrum antibiotic use are key independent risk factors. Early diagnosis and targeted interventions are crucial to improving outcomes in this vulnerable population.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers should focus on minimizing the use of invasive devices and broad-spectrum antibiotics in neonates, and implement early screening protocols for those at high risk of candidemia. Further research is needed to develop and evaluate preventive strategies and treatment protocols tailored for neonatal candidemia.

Keywords: Candidemia, Neonates, NICU, Risk Factors, Mortality.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Candidemia, a bloodstream infection caused by *Candida* species, represents a significant challenge in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) and sick newborn care units (SNCUs) worldwide. This fungal infection is particularly concerning in neonates due to their immature immune systems, making them highly susceptible to invasive infections. The incidence of candidemia has been rising, especially in low birth weight and preterm infants, who often require prolonged hospitalization and invasive procedures, such as central venous catheterization and mechanical ventilation. These factors, coupled with the frequent use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, create an environment conducive to the growth and dissemination of *Candida* species in neonatal populations [1].

The global burden of candidemia in neonates has been increasingly recognized, with studies indicating a mortality rate ranging from 20% to 50%, depending on the population and healthcare setting [2]. In low-resource settings, the incidence may be even higher due to challenges in early diagnosis and limited access to antifungal therapies. The most common species implicated in neonatal candidemia are *Candida albicans* and *Candida parapsilosis*, although non-albicans species have been increasingly reported, which are often associated with higher resistance to standard antifungal treatments [3].

The pathogenesis of candidemia in neonates is complex and multifactorial. Premature infants, in particular, are at high risk due to the

underdevelopment of their skin and mucosal barriers, which are critical in preventing microbial invasion. The use of parenteral nutrition, which often contains lipids, can also promote fungal growth in central venous catheters, providing a direct route for *Candida* species to enter the bloodstream [4]. Additionally, the overuse of broad-spectrum antibiotics disrupts the normal bacterial flora, reducing competition and allowing for fungal overgrowth and subsequent bloodstream invasion.

Despite advances in neonatal care, candidemia remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in NICUs. Recent studies have emphasized the importance of early diagnosis and prompt antifungal therapy to improve outcomes. However, the identification of candidemia can be challenging due to its nonspecific clinical presentation and the limitations of current diagnostic methods, which often lead to delays in treatment [5]. Moreover, the rising incidence of antifungal-resistant *Candida* species further complicates the management of this infection, necessitating ongoing surveillance and the development of new therapeutic strategies.

This study aims to evaluate the incidence and risk factors associated with candidemia in neonates.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) and Sick Newborn Care Unit (SNCU) within a tertiary care hospital. The study spanned a period of 06 months.

Participants: A total of 150 neonates admitted to the NICU and SNCU during the study period were included. These neonates were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure the study population accurately represented those at risk for developing candidemia.

Inclusion Criteria

- Neonates admitted to the NICU or SNCU during the study period.
- Newborns diagnosed with or suspected of having sepsis.
- Neonates with clinical signs suggestive of fungal infections, particularly candidemia.
- Parents or guardians provided informed consent for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Neonates with congenital anomalies incompatible with life.

- Newborns discharged or transferred within 24 hours of admission.
- Neonates whose parents or guardians did not provide consent for participation in the study.

Bias: To minimize bias, neonates were consecutively enrolled as they were admitted to the NICU and SNCU. The study avoided selective enrollment, and data collection was carried out prospectively. To address potential measurement bias, the same diagnostic criteria and laboratory methods were consistently applied throughout the study period.

Data Collection: Data was collected using a structured case report form that captured demographic information, clinical details, risk factors, laboratory findings, and outcomes. Blood cultures were obtained from all participants to identify the presence of *Candida* species. Other relevant laboratory tests were performed as per standard protocols.

Procedure: Upon admission, eligible neonates were screened for inclusion. Blood samples were collected aseptically for culture and other relevant investigations. The neonates were monitored closely, and clinical data were recorded daily, including vital signs, laboratory results, and therapeutic interventions. Blood culture results were followed up, and confirmed cases of candidemia were recorded and analyzed.

Statistical Analysis: The data collected was entered into a database and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, such as mean, median, and standard deviation, were used to summarize the data. Incidence rates of candidemia were calculated. Logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent risk factors associated with candidemia. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 150 neonates were included in the study. The mean gestational age was 30.5 ± 3.2 weeks, with a range of 26 to 37 weeks. The mean birth weight was 1.4 ± 0.5 kg. Of the 150 neonates, 85 (56.7%) were male, and 65 (43.3%) were female. The majority of the neonates (60%) were born via cesarean section, while the remaining 40% were delivered vaginally. The mean length of stay in the NICU/SNCU was 21.3 ± 7.4 days.

Out of the 150 neonates, 22 (14.7%) were diagnosed with candidemia, confirmed by positive blood cultures for *Candida* species. The incidence rate of candidemia in the NICU/SNCU was 14.7 per 100 admissions.

Table 1: Distribution of Candida Species

Candida Species	Number of Cases (n=22)	Percentage
<i>Candida albicans</i>	11	50.0%
<i>Candida parapsilosis</i>	7	31.8%
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	4	18.2%

Among the 22 cases of candidemia, the most commonly isolated species was *Candida albicans* (50%, n=11), followed by *Candida parapsilosis* (31.8%, n=7), and *Candida glabrata* (18.2%, n=4).

Table 2: Risk Factors Associated with Candidemia

Risk Factor	Candidemia (n=22)	Non-Candidemia (n=128)	p-value
Low Birth Weight (<1.5 kg)	16 (72.7%)	38 (29.7%)	<0.001
Prematurity (<32 weeks)	15 (68.2%)	42 (32.8%)	0.002
Central Venous Catheter Use	19 (86.4%)	70 (54.7%)	0.003
Broad-spectrum Antibiotics	20 (90.9%)	80 (62.5%)	0.005
Total Parenteral Nutrition	18 (81.8%)	65 (50.8%)	0.007

Several risk factors were analyzed to determine their association with the development of candidemia. The significant risk factors identified through univariate analysis included low birth weight, prematurity, prolonged use of central venous catheters, use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, and total parenteral nutrition (TPN).

Table 3: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis

Risk Factor	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Low Birth Weight (<1.5 kg)	4.25	2.01–8.98	0.001
Central Venous Catheter Use	3.76	1.59–8.86	0.002
Broad-spectrum Antibiotics	2.88	1.23–6.76	0.015

To identify independent risk factors for candidemia, a multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed. The analysis revealed that low birth weight (OR: 4.25, 95% CI: 2.01–8.98, p=0.001), central venous catheter use (OR: 3.76, 95% CI: 1.59–8.86, p=0.002), and broad-spectrum antibiotic use (OR: 2.88, 95% CI: 1.23–6.76, p=0.015) were independently associated with an increased risk of developing candidemia.

Table 4: Clinical Outcomes

Outcome	Candidemia (n=22)	Non-Candidemia (n=128)	p-value
Mortality	10 (45.5%)	18 (14.1%)	0.001
Mean Length of Hospital Stay	28.5 ± 6.2 days	19.8 ± 7.1 days	<0.001

Neonates with candidemia had a significantly higher mortality rate compared to those without candidemia. Of the 22 neonates with candidemia, 10 (45.5%) died, compared to 18 (14.1%) of the 128 neonates without candidemia (p=0.001). The mean duration of hospital stay was also significantly longer in the candidemia group (28.5 ± 6.2 days) compared to the non-candidemia group (19.8 ± 7.1 days, p<0.001).

Discussion

The study found a notable incidence of candidemia among neonates admitted to the NICU and SNCU of a tertiary care hospital, with 14.7% of the 150 participants developing this serious fungal infection. The most commonly isolated pathogen was *Candida albicans*, accounting for half of the cases, followed by *Candida parapsilosis* and *Candida glabrata*. This distribution highlights the predominance of *Candida albicans* in neonatal candidemia, which aligns with existing literature, but also underscores the importance of considering other species in clinical management.

Risk factor analysis revealed that neonates with low birth weight, prematurity, use of central venous catheters, broad-spectrum antibiotics, and total

parenteral nutrition were more likely to develop candidemia. The logistic regression analysis identified low birth weight, central venous catheter use, and broad-spectrum antibiotic use as independent predictors of candidemia, with significantly increased odds ratios. These findings suggest that these factors should be carefully monitored in neonates to prevent the onset of candidemia.

Clinical outcomes were significantly worse in neonates with candidemia, who experienced a mortality rate of 45.5%, much higher than the 14.1% seen in non-candidemic neonates. Additionally, those with candidemia had a significantly longer hospital stay, averaging 28.5 days compared to 19.8 days for those without the infection. This indicates that candidemia not only increases the risk of death but also contributes to prolonged hospitalization, which can lead to additional complications and increased healthcare costs.

Overall, the study highlights the serious impact of candidemia in neonatal intensive care settings. The identification of specific risk factors provides valuable insights for healthcare providers, suggesting that early intervention and careful

management of high-risk neonates could potentially reduce the incidence and severity of candidemia, improving outcomes for this vulnerable population.

A prospective study found a 12.94% prevalence of candidemia among low birth weight neonates, with a significant emergence of non-albicans *Candida* species, particularly *Candida krusei*. The study underscored the need for heightened prevention and treatment measures to address the morbidity and mortality associated with these infections [6].

A study also reported on the increasing rates of candidemia in NICUs, noting that non-albicans *Candida* species, especially *Candida tropicalis*, have become more prevalent. The study, conducted in Egypt, found that these infections often have an ominous prognosis, with significant resistance to several antifungal agents, thus necessitating regular surveillance and disciplined infection control practices [7].

A study reviewed candidemia trends over seven years in a tertiary hospital in Spain, documenting a high incidence in NICUs. The study found that while *Candida albicans* remained the most frequent species, there was a rising incidence of non-albicans species such as *Candida parapsilosis*, especially in pediatric intensive care units. The persistence of high mortality rates among preterm infants highlighted the need for continuous evaluation of diagnostic and treatment practices [8].

Another study examined fungal sepsis in very low birth weight neonates in an Indian tertiary care center and reported a candidemia incidence of 36%. The study emphasized the growing resistance to antifungal agents, highlighting the critical need for early diagnosis and appropriate treatment to reduce morbidity and mortality in this vulnerable population [9].

In Bangladesh, a study found that low birth weight, prematurity, and prolonged hospital stays were significant risk factors for candidemia in neonates. Their study reported a 60% incidence of candidemia among preterm infants, with a survival rate of 63.3%, underscoring the severe impact of fungal sepsis on neonatal health outcomes [10].

Conclusion

The study demonstrates a significant incidence of candidemia among neonates in the NICU and SNCU, with *Candida albicans* being the most commonly isolated species. Low birth weight, central venous catheter use, and broad-spectrum antibiotic use were identified as independent risk factors for candidemia. The presence of candidemia was associated with higher mortality and longer

hospital stays, underscoring the importance of early detection and targeted interventions in this vulnerable population.

References

1. Benjamin DK, Poole C, Steinbach WJ, Rowen JL, Walsh TJ, Wilson JT, et al. Neonatal candidemia and end-organ damage: a critical appraisal of the literature using meta-analytic techniques. *Pediatrics*. 2003 Jan;112(3 Pt 1):63-4-40.
2. Turner SA, Butler G. The *Candida* Pathogenic Species Complex. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med*. 2014 Nov 20;4(9).
3. Logan C, Beardsley J, Ho KM. *Candida* in neonatal intensive care: The association between prophylactic fluconazole, drug-resistant *Candida*, and *Candida parapsilosis* infection. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2020 Jul 17;71(2):415-21.
4. Hornik CP, Fort P, Clark RH, Watt K, Benjamin DK Jr, Smith PB, et al. Early and late onset sepsis in very-low-birth-weight infants from a large group of neonatal intensive care units. *Early Hum Dev*. 2012 May;88(Suppl 2).
5. Patel RM, Kandefer S, Walsh MC, Bell EF, Carlo WA, Laptook AR, et al. Causes and timing of death in extremely premature infants from 2000 through 2011. *N Engl J Med*. 2015 Jan 22;372(4):331-40.
6. Jahan T, Farhana A, Nargis S. Persisting non-albicans candidemia in low birth weight neonates in a tertiary care hospital, Jammu and Kashmir. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2023. doi:10.18203/2320-6012.ijrms20231055.
7. Hassan D, Yousef R, Abu El-Hamed WA, Ali AA, Madkour L. Candidemia in the neonatal intensive care unit: Insights on epidemiology and antifungal drug susceptibility patterns. *Arch Pediatr Infect Dis*. 2018. doi:10.5812/PEDINFECT.81090.
8. Piqueras A, Rubio T, López-Medina E, Gimeno A, Modesto V, Cantón E, Pemán J. Recent changes in candidemia trends in a tertiary hospital (2011-2018). *Rev Iberoam Micol*. 2020. doi:10.1016/j.riam.2020.09.005.
9. Bhosale D, Nanoti G, Dwivedi S, Dahat A. Prevalence of fungal sepsis in low birth weight and very low birth weight neonates and its correlation with high risk factors in a tertiary care centre in India. *Int J Sci Res*. 2023. doi:10.36106/ijsr/5323454.
10. Tasneem F, Hossain M, Mahmud S, Ahmed SS. Clinical profile of fungal sepsis in newborn: a tertiary centre experience from Bangladesh. *J Pediatr Neonatal Care*. 2020. doi:10.15406/JPNC.2020.10.00432.